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Organic Radical Epoxy Thermoset

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Conductive processes in polymer systems

Organic Radical Epoxy Thermoset

Synthetic Methodology

Continuous Flow Synthesis of Epoxy Monomer

Characterization

- TGA Analysis

Significance of Study

- ❖ intrinsic conductivity = “industry 4.0 materials”.
- ❖ new polymeric platform = ORP chemistry + physico-chemical characteristics of ORP
- ❖ new epoxy monomer = multifunctional epoxy resin + new conductive composites + coatings + redox catalysts + organic magnets + energy storage systems.

Organic Radical Thermosets

Thank You

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